

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LARGEST STUDY ON GENETIC RISK FOR TYPE 2 DIABETES

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Abstract

The diabetes field has long classified the disorder into genetically distinct groups, including type 1 and type 2. However, new genetics research focused on a form of type 2 diabetes (T2D) that is becoming more common in adolescents suggests a more complicated picture. Researchers at the Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, Boston Children's Hospital, and Harvard Medical School analyzed DNA from more than 3,000 T2D participants between 12 and 18-years-old and nearly 9,800 adult controls, more than three-quarters of whom were of African American or Hispanic ancestry. They found that youth-onset T2D is a genetically intermediate form of the disorder that lies on a spectrum between adult-onset T2D and rare forms of the disorder caused by a single gene. Adult-onset T2D is influenced by thousands of common genetic variants, whereas the rare genetic forms, known as monogenic diabetes, are caused by a single variant. Moreover, these individuals harbored more of these variants than people with adult-onset T2D, suggesting that genetics has a larger role in causing youth-onset T2D than in the adult-onset form. The work also revealed that the specific mix of different types of variants a given individual carried correlated with their particular set of symptoms. For example, those with more common variants showed more symptoms of adult-onset T2D, such as high insulin levels. Disease-causing genetic variants are generally classified as common (appearing in more than 5 percent in the population), rare (less than 1 to 5 percent of population), or monogenic (which are able to cause disease on their own). Teasing apart the contributions of these different types of variants in youth-onset T2D risk requires genetic data from thousands of patients.

Keywords: diabetes, endocrine system, risk, adult

Diabetes, a disease of the endocrine system diagnosed by abnormally high blood glucose levels, is one of the most common and fastest growing diseases worldwide, projected to affect 693 million adults by 2045, a >50% increase from 2017. Vascular complications of both the macro- and microvascular systems (cardiovascular disease [CVD], diabetic kidney disease [DKD], diabetic retinopathy [DR], and neuropathy) are the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in individuals with diabetes, carrying enormous financial burden with unequal healthcare expenditure and access to treatment between developed and developing countries. While the precise mechanisms of hyperglycemia-induced vascular damage are both complex and not fully understood, it is thought that high levels of intracellular glucose increase the production of reactive oxygen species altering a series of critical downstream pathways, including polyol pathway flux, advanced glycation end product formation and activation, protein kinase C activation, and hexosamine pathway flux. Diabetes is not a single disease, but rather a group of conditions broadly categorized by a single diagnostic criterion – hyperglycemia, the final common pathway on which disparate metabolic derangements converge. It is becoming increasingly evident that even type 2 diabetes (T2D), the predominant diabetes subtype making up 90–95% of cases, is itself heterogeneous in terms of both the mechanisms of action and the relationships with health outcomes. Recent clustering approaches using clinical or genetic biomarkers have identified subtypes of T2D that are clinically distinct and differentially associated with diabetic complications. Namely, these studies find an increased risk for decreased renal function among individuals assigned to various insulin

resistance clusters, an increased risk for DR among those in the clinical severe insulin deficiency cluster, and an increased risk for coronary artery disease (CAD) among the reduced beta-cell function and lipodystrophy-like fat distribution genetic clusters. Intriguingly, there were no significant differences among the clinical clusters of Ahlqvist *et al.* for coronary events after adjusting for age and sex. Furthermore, vascular damage can occur through non-hyperglycemic mechanisms, some of which are also diabetes comorbidities such as hypertension and obesity, further complicating genetic research, diagnosis, and potentially management of hyperglycemia-induced vascular damage.

Current approaches to diabetes complications do not reverse the process, but rely almost exclusively on imperfect attempts at prevention or management of established pathology. On top of landmark studies that show clear decline in both onset and progression of vascular diabetes complications through intensive glucose-lowering treatments, individuals with diabetes can further reduce their risk for complications by lowering blood pressure and taking antihypertensive medications (angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers) that inhibit the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system and reduce the risk of complications via blood pressure-dependent and independent mechanisms. More recently, certain classes of glucose-lowering agents (SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP1 receptor agonists) have demonstrated marked reductions in ESKD and CVD-related outcomes in patients with T2D apparently due to both glucose-dependent and independent mechanisms. Interestingly, loss-of-function mutations in the *SLC5A2* gene encoding

SGLT2, the major glucose cotransporter in the proximal tubule of the kidney, are known to cause familial renal glycosuria, a disease characterized by decreased renal glucose reabsorption and increased glucose excretion. This paradigm illustrates that exploring the genetics of glucose dysfunction diseases as well as the interaction between genetics and treatment may provide insight into the clinical success of novel therapeutics. Beyond medication and lifestyle changes that slow progression of disease, the majority of treatments of late-stage disease involve either dialysis or transplant for kidney disease or other surgical interventions (i.e. laser photocoagulation eye surgery or amputation).

We also report, to our knowledge, the only multi-ethnic data on changes in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in youth. The prevalence of type 2 diabetes in 2009 among adolescents aged 10 through 19 years was 0.46 per 1000 or 0.046%, with highest prevalence in American Indians, followed by black, Hispanic, and Asian Pacific Islander youth, with lowest prevalence in white youth, a pattern that is almost the inverse of that seen in type 1 diabetes. Prevalence was somewhat lower than reported in fifth- to 12th-grade students in Ohio (0.08%, previously diagnosed type 2 diabetes), although a higher proportion of black students were included in that study. It was also lower than the screening results in the Studies to Treat or Prevent Pediatric Type 2 Diabetes (STOPP-T2D) involving eighth-grade students, which documented a 0.5% prevalence of elevated screening glucose levels; however, only a single screening test was used. Compared with our estimate of 0.46 per 1000, the reported prevalence among sixth graders in the HEALTHY study (0.2 per 1000) was lower, as was prevalence among students in the Philadelphia schools (0.35 per 1000 overall), which also reported substantially lower race/ethnicity specific estimates (0.03 per 1000 white; 0.28 per 1000 black; and 0.05 per 1000 Hispanic youth).

We showed that the overall prevalence of type 2 diabetes between 2001 and 2009 increased by 30.5% when adjusted for differences in completeness of ascertainment. Increases occurred in white, Hispanic, and black youth, whereas no changes were found in Asian Pacific Islander and American Indian youth. Projections suggest that the number of youth with type 2 diabetes will increase from 22 820 in 2010 to 84 131 in 2050, a 4-fold increase. Our data also suggest that there was little change in the pattern of diagnosis of diabetes type that clinicians used over this period, with the exception of white youth. We can only speculate about whether changes in the awareness of type 2 diabetes in youth over time may have accounted for this change. Because a lower proportion of white youth met the etiologic criteria in the first period, the rates for 2001 may have been overestimated, and therefore we may have underestimated the increase in type 2 diabetes among white youth.

There are limited population-based data on temporal trends of type 2 diabetes in youth. In Cincinnati, Ohio, type 2 diabetes incidence increased 10-fold, from 1982 to 1994 (average annual change, 41.7%). Annual incidence rates from 1994 to 2003 increased by 3.7%

among white, 3.9% among black, and 9.6% among Hispanic children with insulin-treated, non-type 1 diabetes in Chicago however, these case patients represent an unknown proportion of all case patients. Among aboriginal youth in Alberta, Canada, a 14% average annual increase was reported between 1995 and 2007 in youth younger than 20 years. Dabelea et al showed an increase in prevalence of type 2 diabetes in Pima Indian youth aged 10 through 19 years in both sexes, with the highest prevalence in females. In Pima, the estimated average annual increase ranged from 1.9% to 10%, whereas we estimated the average annual increase at 4.4% overall, similar to that seen among the Pima Indians.

Studies in Europe indicate that type 2 diabetes remains rare in largely white populations, and 1 report showed no trend; however, we observed a significant prevalence increase in white youth. Although differences in obesity rates between US and European youth are likely contributors, the full explanation for these discrepancies deserves further study.

Several reasons for the increasing type 2 diabetes prevalence are possible. Most likely are real changes in population risk for type 2 diabetes, such as minority population growth, obesity, exposure to diabetes in utero, and perhaps endocrine-disrupting chemicals. Similarly, changing awareness of type 2 diabetes in youth leading to different diagnostic practices may have contributed to the increases.

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